

ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF SELF-ALLIGNED *IN-SITU* REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDE/EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

N. Yousefi, X. Y. Lin, X. Shen, J. J. Jia, O. J. Dada, J. K. Kim*

Department of Mechanical Engineering, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Clear Water Bay, Kowloon, Hong Kong

* Corresponding author (mejkkim@ust.hk)

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Abstract

Self-aligned *in-situ* reduced graphene oxide (rGO)/waterborne epoxy (EP) nanocomposite were prepared using an all aqueous method. The nanocomposites delivered a very low percolation threshold of 0.26 wt% as a result of the fine dispersion of monolayer rGO sheets and their ultralarge size. The rGO/EP nanocomposites exhibited exceptionally high dielectric constant arising from the charge accumulation at the highly conductive filler/insulating polymer interface according to Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars polarization principle. The highly dielectric rGO/EP nanocomposites can function as effective electromagnetic interference shielding materials.

1 Introduction

In the past few decades, polymers have emerged as versatile, cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternatives to a wide range of engineering materials. However, most polymers suffer from low electrical conductivity which limits their application in electronics industries. To tackle this problem, conductive carbon materials, such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), carbon black (CB) [1] and more recently, graphene [2, 3], have been added to insulating polymers to prepare conductive composites. In this case, the dispersion state of nanofillers and their possible assembly into engineered nanostructures largely determine the overall electrical properties of the nanocomposites. The critical concentration of conducting fillers above which the conductivity of the polymer nanocomposites abruptly increases, or the percolation threshold, is influenced by many parameters, including the aspect ratio, dispersion state and inherent conductivity of the conductive fillers [1].

Graphene, as the most-recently discovered member of carbon allotropes and with its exceptionally high carrier mobility and ballistic electron transport properties, is a prime nanofiller to be used in nanocomposites for electrical applications [4]. As a precursor for graphene, graphene oxide (GO) enjoys an abundance of versatile oxygen-containing groups on its edges and basal planes which render its high processability and dispersibility in aqueous solutions. These ameliorating properties make GO an ideal choice for preparation of well-dispersed nanocomposites with an engineered nanostructure and interphase. However, GO suffers from lack of electrical conductivity due to the disruption of its conjugated backbone by the oxygenated groups. Therefore, an additional reduction step is often required to restore its electrical conductivity [5]. Reduced GO (rGO) has been used in conjunction with a wide variety of polymers to prepare conductive polymer nanocomposites. Percolation thresholds as low as 0.08 and 0.12 vol.% have been reported in our studies on self-aligned rGO/waterborne polyurethane (PU) [2] and rGO/epoxy (EP) [3] nanocomposites, respectively. The ultralarge size of GO, its self-assembly into a layered structure and the excellent dispersion of rGO in waterborne PU and EP were the main reasons behind these remarkably low percolation thresholds. With the low percolation threshold of the produced nanocomposites and their engineered layered structure in mind, there is a good potential for them to be used in such applications as high dielectric and EMI shielding materials. This paper investigates the electrical properties of rGO/EP nanocomposites with particular emphasis on studying the mechanisms of electrical conduction, dielectric properties and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding behavior of the nanocomposites.

2 Experimental

GO was produced based on the modified Hummers method [6, 7]. To prepare groups of GO sheets with different sizes, the unsorted dispersion was centrifuged at increasingly lower speeds, namely 8000 (first round), 6000 (second round) and 4000 rpm (third round) for 40 min at each round. The supernatant was removed after the completion of each round and the precipitate re-dispersed in water to be centrifuged in the following round. The supernatant of the first, second and third rounds were collected as small (S), large (L) and very large (VL) GO, respectively, while the precipitate of the third round of centrifugation was collected to label as ultralarge (UL) GO [8].

The process used to prepare EP-based composites was essentially identical to that reported previously [3]. Aqueous GO dispersion with a concentration of 1 mg/ml was mixed with epoxy latex and reduced with hydrazine at a GO:hydrazine ratio of 3:1 at 80 °C. Waterborne hardener at a ratio of epoxy:hardener = 5:1 was added to the reduced mixture. The mixture was cured at 60 °C for 24 hrs to obtain homogenous nanocomposite films. GO/EP and rGO/EP nanocomposites with different graphene contents were prepared.

The structure of the nanocomposites was studied using a transmission electron microscope (TEM). The size distributions of GO and rGO sheets in dispersions were measured using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The electrical conductivity of cured nanocomposites was measured using a four-point probe in the plane direction and a curve-tracer in the thickness direction. The EMI shielding efficiency was measured using a network analyzer. The dielectric properties were measured on an impedance analyzer.

3 Results and Discussion

In line with our previous studies [2, 3, 9], the typical size of monolayer GO sheets used in this study ranged from a few to a few hundreds of micrometers in lateral length. The area distributions of GO and rGO sheets were obtained by analyzing the SEM images of the nanosheets (Fig 1a-b).

The average area of GO sheets and the extracted rGO sheets after reduction were 191.3 and 176.4 μm^2 , respectively [3]. This indicates that the *in-situ* reduction process for converting GO to rGO sheets

had negligible effects on their average size and size distribution.

The dispersion and morphology of the nanocomposites were studied using TEM (Fig 1c-d). The graphene sheets were exfoliated and dispersed very well at both low and high contents. At a low rGO content of 0.5 wt.%, no particular order was seen and the nanosheets were randomly oriented in the matrix. At a high rGO content of 2.0 wt.%, a distinctive layered structure was observed. In other words, upon evaporation of water, the graphene sheets were self-aligned into a layered structure. The self-alignment was possible as a result of (i) ultralarge size of GO, (ii) low viscose waterborne epoxy and (iii) the long water evaporation time used in this study [3].

The self-aligned layered structure resulted in highly anisotropic properties between the directions of alignment and that perpendicular to it. The directional dependence of the properties was absent in the nanocomposites with low graphene contents which are essentially isotropic in nature.

Fig 1. Area distribution of (a) GO and (b) rGO sheets and their typical SEM images as inset (scale bar = 50 μm); and TEM micrographs of EP nanocomposites containing (a) 0.5 wt% and (b) 2 wt% rGO showing random and self-aligned layered nanostructures, respectively [3].

The electrical conductivities of the nanocomposites were measured both along the alignment direction and that perpendicular to it (Fig 2a). The conductivity of GO/EP nanocomposites was very low, at about 10^{-12} S/cm, regardless of GO concentrations as a result of the insulating nature of GO sheets. Upon *in-situ* reduction, the electrical

conductivity of rGO was restored and the conductivity of nanocomposites varied with rGO content. The percolation threshold was measured to be 0.26 wt.% (0.12 vol.%). The large-size monolayer graphene nanosheets used in this study as well as their excellent dispersion in epoxy as a result of the all-aqueous processing method used are among the reasons behind the remarkably low percolation threshold.

It is of interest to note that the electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites measured along the two directions were identical up to about 1 wt.% rGO, reaffirming the isotropy and random dispersion of graphene sheets at a low content. However, at graphene contents above this critical value, the conductivity varied differently depending on the direction of measurement: while the conductivity measured in the alignment direction consistently increased, that measured in the perpendicular to it decreased with increasing rGO content. This observation is the consequence of the self-alignment of graphene sheets into a layered structure where there are more electrical contacts between the rGO sheets along the direction of alignment, in comparison with the direction perpendicular to it.

To understand the fundamental mechanism of electrical conduction in nanocomposites, the temperature-dependence of conductivity was measured at different rGO contents (Fig 2b). The conductivity of nanocomposites with low rGO contents, say below 0.5 wt.%, was highly temperature-dependent and the value increased by a few orders of magnitude when the composites were heated from ambient to 100 °C. However, at high rGO contents, the conductivity was increasingly less temperature-dependent, and for the nanocomposites containing 1 wt.% rGO or above, the conductivity marginally decreased with increasing temperature.

Electrical transport in polymer nanocomposites can occur either through direct “contacts” between the conductive fillers or “tunneling” of electrons between the sufficiently close particles [10]. In the former case, the conductive fillers physically contact one another to form a conductive network and the electrons can transport like they do in a typical inherently conducting material. In this case, an increase in temperature promotes the lattice vibrations and disrupts the transport of electrons, resulting in a reduction in conductivity. However, in the “tunneling” phenomenon, the electrons can

literally tunnel between two sufficiently close conductive fillers which are separated by a thin layer of polymer. In this case, an increase in temperature enhances the mobility of electrons and reduces the energy barrier of tunneling, resulting in a tangible improvement in conductivity [10].

Fig 2. Electrical conductivities of GO/EP and rGO/EP nanocomposites as a function of (a) graphene content [3] and (b) temperature.

The highly temperature-dependent nature of the nanocomposites at a low graphene content can be related to the dominance of the tunneling mechanism when the graphene sheets are not abundant enough to physically touch each other. The extent of temperature-dependence became less noticeable when the rGO content increased above the percolation threshold and finally the conductivity became almost constant when the rGO content was above about 2-3 wt.%. At this point, the physical contacts between the fillers are well developed and “contact” conductivity dominates over the tunneling

mechanism. The slight decrease in conductivity with increasing temperature is an evidence for the prominent role of contact conductivity in these composites.

Polymer nanocomposites containing conductive carbon fillers have been widely used as potential high dielectric (high-k) materials for various applications, such as embedded capacitors, electroactive polymers for artificial muscles and flexible batteries [11]. High-k materials can store a significant amount of electrical charge. Traditionally ferroelectric ceramic materials, such as barium titanate, have been used as high-k materials. The high dielectric constant of these materials originate from the displacement of ionic centers in the crystalline structure under the influence of an external electric field, resulting in asymmetrical shift of the ionic centers and polarization in the crystalline lattice [12].

Ceramic dielectrics suffer from inherent brittleness which can be overcome by adding powder form of these materials to polymers to obtain flexible dielectric polymer composites. However, more than 30 wt.% ceramic fillers are needed to obtain relatively high dielectric constants, which often causes deterioration of the mechanical properties of the composites [11]. In contrast, polymer nanocomposites consisting of carbon fillers can present high dielectric constants at much lower filler contents, along with benefits of high flexibility and processability.

The high potential of polymer nanocomposites made from carbon fillers originates mainly from the conductivity mismatch between the filler and matrix. According to the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars (MWS) principle, the disparity between the conductivity of two adjacent materials can result in polarization and charge accumulation at their interfaces [11, 13]. Therefore, the dielectric properties of conductive polymer nanocomposites are determined largely by the nature of the filler/matrix interface, filler surface area and the inherent conductivity of the fillers. More importantly, the alignment of the fillers along a certain direction may also play a very important role in obtaining nanocomposites with high dielectric constants.

The dielectric constants of nanocomposites were measured as a function of frequency and temperature (Fig. 3). The neat epoxy and the rGO/EP nanocomposites containing 0.1 wt.% graphene

showed negligible dielectric constants at all frequencies studied. The very low value of about 5 obtained for the neat epoxy fell within the range reported in the literature [14]. The dielectric properties of conductive polymers follow a percolative pattern. Above the electrical percolation threshold, the conductive networks formed by the nanofillers contribute synergistically to storing the electrical charge at their interfaces with the insulating polymer, hence a highly dielectric nanocomposite. Therefore, the dielectric constants drastically improved, reaching a value as high as about 15,000 in the composites with 3 wt.% rGO.

Fig 3. Dielectric constants of rGO/EP nanocomposites as a function of (a) frequency and (b) temperature.

The dielectric constant values were highly frequency-dependent and rapidly decreased with an increase in frequency. The frequency-dependent nature of conductive polymer nanocomposites has been widely reported and is usually attributed to the dissipation of the charge at the filler/matrix interface into heat.

The dielectric constants were also measured at different temperatures (Fig. 3b). The composites maintained high dielectric permittivities even at high

temperatures depending on the rGO content. There was a peak at about 70-80°C which coincides with the typical glass transition temperature of the nanocomposites [3]. The dielectric constant of polymers showed a peak in the vicinity of their T_g as a result of the molecular α -relaxation. Such a peak is often attributed to the activation and ordering of electric dipoles at the glass transition when molecules start to vibrate vigorously [15]. However, the orientation of the activated electric dipoles is disrupted immediately after the transition as a result of increased thermal agitation in the molecules. The observed peak in the nanocomposites (Fig. 3b) can hence be attributed to the participation from epoxy molecules and conform well with the T_g values obtained using other thermal methods [3]. The dielectric constants of the nanocomposites are compared with those reported in literature for similar nanocomposites containing carbon nanofillers (Table 1). It is noted that the dielectric constant obtained in this study was among the highest. This observation can be attributed to several important structural and material characteristics of the fillers and composites produced: (i) ultralarge size of rGO sheets, (ii) excellent dispersion of GO in the waterborne epoxy resin, (iii) preservation of the stability and superior dispersion even after reduction in the entirely *in situ* process, and (iv) self-alignment of the rGO sheets into a layered structure.

Fig 4. Schematic illustration of the formation of numerous nanocapacitors in the nanocomposites.

Among the various mechanisms responsible for the high dielectric constants obtained in this work, self-alignment into a layered structure is of paramount importance. As the main mechanism of dielectric permittivity in these nanocomposites, the MWS polarization across the rGO/EP interface indicates that any pair of adjacent conductive rGO sheets separated by an insulating epoxy thin film can serve as a nanoscale capacitor. Therefore, a typical well-aligned nanocomposite is comprised of a huge

network of nanocapacitors (Fig 4). The huge network containing millions of capacitors has an extremely large capacity for storing electric charges, enabling the conductive polymer nanocomposite to possess a superior dielectric permittivity.

Table 1. Comparison of dielectric constants of nanocomposites containing carbon fillers.

Matrix	Filler	Filler Amount	Dielectric constant	Freq.	
Epoxy	CB	19.6 w%	2400	10 kHz	[16]
PVDF	rGO	0.18 v%	8000	100 Hz	[17]
PFA	CNT	0.6 w%	10500	10 kHz	[18]
PVDF	CNT	8 v%	3600	1 kHz	[19]
PP	rGO	0.2 v%	2000	1 kHz	[20]
Epoxy	rGO	1 w%	4.2	1 MHz	[21]
Epoxy	rGO	3 w%	13752	1 kHz	This work

One of the most significant applications of high-k materials is the shielding of unwanted electromagnetic waves. EMI shielding is particularly important in many electronic products where electronic components should be protected from interference arising from other devices/components, while at the same time they should not emit unwanted electromagnetic waves. Traditionally, metallic coatings or cases have been widely used to shield the unwanted EMI. The heavy weight of metallic EMI shields is undesirable, especially for mobile devices such as laptop computers and smart phones, thus lighter alternatives to metals have been sought, in particular among polymer-based composites.

rGO/EP nanocomposites, as highly conductive as well as high-dielectric materials, can serve as ideal EMI shielding materials to block unwanted electromagnetic noise in electronic devices. The EMI shielding efficiency of GO/EP and rGO/EP nanocomposites were measured (Fig 7). As expected, the EMI shielding efficiency of GO/EP nanocomposites was very low, at about 11-12 dB regardless of GO content, and marginally higher than about 3 dB corresponding to the neat epoxy. The insulating nature of GO sheets resulted in insulating nanocomposites with no potential for EMI shielding.

In contrast, adding rGO has an ameliorating effect in increasing the EMI shielding efficiency of epoxy.

The shielding efficiency was as high as 40 dB for the composites containing 3 wt.% rGO, which is considered among the highest values reported in open media. The highly-aligned rGO sheets in the composites also contributed positively to shielding the electromagnetic waves in a more efficient way. Effective EMI shielding materials either reflect the incidental EM waves or absorb them. The exceptionally high EMI shielding efficiency of the rGO/EP nanocomposites is considered arising from their high charge storage capacity. In other words, the high-k nanocomposites can absorb the incidental EM waves by polarization in the electric field.

mismatch between epoxy and rGO sheets resulted in interfacial polarization under an electric field which led to high charge storage capacities with associated exceptionally high dielectric constants for the rGO/EP nanocomposites. The large rGO sheets and their alignment into a layered structure played a dominant role in achieving such unique dielectric properties. The parallel rGO sheets and the interleaved epoxy thin film constituted a network consisting of numerous nanocapacitors that rendered an extremely high charge storage capacity to the nanocomposites. The high-k rGO/EP nanocomposites could serve as effective EMI shielding materials due to their high charge absorbing properties.

Fig 7. EMI shielding efficiencies of (a) neat epoxy and GO/EP nanocomposites; and (b) rGO/EP nanocomposites.

4 Conclusions

Graphene/epoxy nanocomposites were prepared using an all-aqueous method to obtain self-aligned nanocomposites with anisotropic properties along the in-plane and thickness directions. The nanocomposites containing well-dispersed and ultralarge rGO nanosheets had a very low percolation threshold of 0.26 wt.%. The conductivity

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